

Advanced Energy Management for Demand Response and Microgeneration Integration

C. Abreu¹, D. Rua¹, P. Machado¹ J. A. Peças Lopes^{1,2}
1-INESC TEC, 2-FEUP
Porto, Portugal
{crabreu, drua, paam}@inesctec.pt, jpl@fe.up.pt

Miguel Heleno
Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory
Berkeley, United States
miguelheleno@lbl.gov

Abstract—Energy management is a key tool that will enable consumers to optimize their energy use according to different objectives. Allow users to insert their energy use preferences combined with the effective configuration and control of existing devices (loads and microgeneration) is the basis, in this paper, to design adaptable energy optimization algorithms that are capable to outputting feasible, understandable and useful actions, automated and/or manual, for the activation of the existing portfolio of flexible devices. This paper presents an advanced energy management system as an innovative platform that intends to accomplish real energy optimization schemes to support demand response, promote the energy efficiency and contribute towards renewable integration.

Index Terms—Energy, Optimization, Management, System

I. INTRODUCTION

Energy management in the home domain needs solutions that 1) allow end-users to easily insert their comfort preferences and appliances usage and 2) generate efficient load scheduling and control strategies, based on the information provided, to achieve costs savings and/or CO₂ reduction. These strategies, considering existence of both automated and manual consumption devices and systems, have also the potential to enable the participation of households in grid-related ancillary services provision, such as Demand Response (DR) [1]. Additionally, with the increasing adoption of behind-the-meter generation in the domestic sector, e.g. rooftop PV, home energy management solutions also need to take into account microgeneration units to enhance the efficiency of these strategies and increase the potential benefits for the end-users.

Despite the proven economic and social value of controlling behind-the-meter Distributed Energy Resources (DERs), the market is still waiting for a disruptive technological solution for energy management in the home domain, capable of leading to a mass adoption and contribute to a large-scale impact. The technological challenges in this field can be divided in

three dimensions: 1) the development of a flexible architecture to support and integrate a variety of systems, including communication and control of appliances and microgeneration devices, integration of multiple energy vectors (electricity, gas, heat), interoperability with existing ICT infrastructure in the home environment, information exchange with utilities and retailers, etc.; 2) the implementation of optimal energy management strategies to schedule and control multiple DERs, yielding effective energy savings and facilitating the provision of new services to the grid; 3) the design of attractive and responsive end-user interfaces capable of engaging electricity customers, increasing energy awareness and producing behavioral changes through concise information.

With the aim of responding to these technological challenges, the AnyPLACE solution was created as an energy management platform where tailor-made multi-device user interfaces, adaptable energy management algorithms and an automation platform allow end-users to implement energy efficiency actions. This platform was developed under the framework of the AnyPLACE H2020 project that intends to create a cost-effective solution to be deployed in the context of domestic building. Thus, the objective of this paper is to propose an energy management optimization method, implemented in the AnyPLACE platform, to perform an optimal scheduling of different types of domestic loads, for the day ahead, taking into account their flexibility and behind-the-meter PV generation.

In section II is presented the related work within the scope of the work presented in this paper. Section III introduces the energy management methodology that is used to produce optimized schedules of appliances and microgeneration systems for the next day. Section IV presents a set of scenarios, likely to be found in households, and where energy optimization procedures are expected to be used. In section V an energy management platform is presented, in which the energy management algorithms are embedded, to be deployed in real households. The main conclusions from the work presented in this paper are drawn in VI.

II. RELATED WORK

The concept of the Home Energy Management Systems (HEMS) emerged under the name of Energy Box within

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multiple projects in the first decade of the 21st century [2]-[3]. The initial idea consisted of a central unit located in a domestic building capable of performing an optimized control of behind-the-meter resources to minimize the energy costs, considering weather conditions, local generation units as well as the thermal model of the house and the outdoor temperature [4]. Later, the optimization functionalities were extended to advanced services to the grid, such as demand response (DR) [3].

Domestic Thermostatically Controlled Loads (TCL), such as HVAC systems and Hot Water Heaters (HWH) have traditionally been a valuable resource for DR by the utilities in the past. However, recent proliferation of Internet of Things (IoT) and smart appliances provided these loads with a finer degree of controllability, allowing domestic appliances to report real-time consumption information and receiving set-point from [5]. Hence, methodologies for load management of TCL dealing with real-time data, e.g. considering the possibility of these appliances to report their current temperature and on/off state to the house central controller, started being proposed [6]. The new conditions for control allowed the loads to respond to real-time energy prices [7] and to participate in ancillary services markets [8]. In this context, the HEMS play a vital role in converting the appliances control into actual services exchange with the retailers and the grid, for example by scheduling loads for the provision of reserve [9].

However, besides facilitating external services, HEMS load control capabilities can also be used for other purposes within the home domain. A popular application nowadays is the control of behind-the-meter flexible resources to maximize PV self-consumption, especially after the regulatory incentives to reduce PV grid injections in some European countries [10]. Again, TCL has been used as a primary load resource to provide flexibility, namely space heating and EWHs [11]. For instance, in [12], the authors propose a model predictive control for scheduling the consumption of an EWH with the objective of following PV generation and, in [13], an optimization model aiming at maximizing PV based self-consumption in the day ahead scheduling of an EWH is presented. This paper expands these optimization models to additional loads in the home domain, AC and shiftable loads (e.g. washers and dryers), in order to maximize self-consumption. This day ahead optimal scheduling method is implemented in the AnyPLACE platform where the comfort parameters of end-users, acting as a constraint of the optimization problem, are provided to the HEMS through a graphical user interface.

III. ENERGY MANAGEMENT METHODOLOGY

The energy management methodology used in this work takes into account the internal inputs derived from the home domain and the external inputs received by service providers that are interested in shaping the response in the energy use of specific households. Taking that into account, different optimization criterion can be considered that will establish the way the optimization process is conducted.

The available information from the home domain and from the external sources is used by the methodology, presented in this section, to produce an optimized schedule of appliances as well as existing microgeneration to be activated in the next day, considering a multi-temporal optimization procedure carried out with some time in advance. The procedure will be associated to an energy management system platform that will be responsible for storing preferences and configurations and produce the optimized schedule.

A. Home Domain

The internal inputs used by the energy management system are associated to the home domain, in which appliances operate according to specific preferences and configuration settings. The underlying features of appliances and comfort preferences set by users determine the flexibility of the energy use in each household. As such, it is fundamental to characterize, as much as possible, the energy use within the home domain.

1) *Appliances Modeling*: In order to characterize the appliances that are suitable to be reschedule is necessary to understand which ones have the higher consumption and if the new schedule will not bring any discomfort to the end user. To this end, two different types of appliances were considered: shiftables and thermal appliances.

Shiftable appliances operate on a predefined cycle with a known duration and consumption. The idea is to schedule their operation for low-priced periods. The model of these appliances are based on historical data retrieved from the house, or using default consumption patterns. This system can control and monitor the smart shiftable appliances through a direct communication and the manual ones through a smart plug.

To characterize the behavior of residential thermostatically controlled loads, physically-based load models were used [14] and were considered two representative types: air conditioner and electric water heater. The modeling of these appliances required a significant amount of information regarding distinct aspects of appliances and consumption. The necessary information on the characteristics of the household appliances as installation environment are: thermal capacities, thermal resistances/admittances and nominal electric power. Also, some inputs are needed regarding the consumption habits, such as the periods when the AC is running or the typical end-user's shower hot water usage (time and quantity).

2) *User Preferences*: The preferences set by users in an energy management platform can be quite complex and introduce additional challenges in defining an optimal schedule for the following day. In order to overcome these challenges, the system was configured to consider several possible schedule parameters that the end user can modify according to his preferences and appliances type. In general user preferences are treated as restrictions, added to the optimization problem formulation, and as such they need to be carefully considered

under the penalty of not being able to create a viable space of solutions for the problem.

For shiftable appliances the user has the possibility to choose one or more deadlines (depending how many times the appliance is going to work that day) with a maximum operation span of 24h. A time window is available between a configuration time and deadline, during which the control method can choose the optimal start time. If the appliances are manual with no possibility of remote control, the user must indicate a time interval in which the appliance can be connected manually.

For thermal appliances the consumer can set his comfort requirements such as the desired hot water temperature and the usual number of baths per period, for the following day (e.g. “2 baths @ 7:00 am and 1 bath @ 8:00 pm”).

The end-user may impose further restrictions to the optimization problem by adding a power cap or contracted power limits. However, this introduces additional challenges as it necessitates further characterization of the power consumption baseline and the inflexible loads through direct measurement or estimation.

B. External Interaction

The energy management algorithms incorporate functions capable of dealing also with external information. This information includes tariff publishing (load and generation) and other online services that provide local forecasts for sun irradiance and temperature from one day ahead.

C. Optimization Criterion

The formulation of the optimization problem is dependent of the different criteria that is used and consequently on the level of optimization that can be achieved. Among the wide diversity of optimization criteria that can be associated to an energy management system, the cost is probably the most appealing as it focuses on finding a lower cost for the energy use. If price discrimination follows an efficiency goal from a grid perspective, so will be participants in DR in general.

1) *Cost*: An optimization criteria that can be performed by the AnyPLACE platform, is presented in the objective function (1), where the aim is to find the lowest daily total cost for the energy use.

$$\min \left(\sum_{t=0}^{n_{steps}} C_t \cdot \left[\sum_{j=1}^n \sum_{i=0}^{d_j} [P_i^j \times \lambda_{t-i}^j] + \sum_{k=1}^m [P_t^m \times \lambda_t^m] \right] \right) \quad (1)$$

$$\text{s.t.:} \quad P_{uLt} + P_t^m + P_t^j \leq P_{CP}$$

$$\sum_{t=0}^{D_j-d_j} \lambda_t^j = 1$$

where:

- n_{steps} , number of control periods
- n , number of shiftable appliances
- d_j , duration of operation of appliance j

- P_i^j , power in period i of appliance j
- m , number of thermal appliances
- λ_{t-i}^j , binary variable-condition if appliance start in period $t-i$
- λ_t^m , binary variable-condition if appliance is operating or not
- P_t^m , capacity of thermal appliance m
- P_{uLt} , uncontrollable loads
- P_{CP} , contracted power
- C_t , electricity costs

This model is constrained by the number of times that a shiftable appliance can work per day, by the thermal comfort limits imposed by the end-user [14] and by the house power contractual limitation. This last constraint is very relevant since in some European countries there is a limitation of the instantaneous power that can be drawn from the grid. This represents an additional cost in the electricity bill and it is usually associated to discrete power interval values.

2) *Self-Consumption*: Regarding the Photovoltaic (PV) self-consumption in countries like Germany and Portugal, a new policy was implemented to encourage instantaneous consumption. For instance, the recent Portuguese legislation for small PV installations announces lower remuneration for PV energy fed into the grid in comparison with the retailing energy price for the consumption. This makes self-consumption always more profitable (or less expensive) than injecting PV into the grid.

Since a significant part of the users are not at home during the day, it is necessary a modification of the consumption profile to shift the loads for periods with higher PV generation.

The optimal scheduling for the day-ahead considering PV involves solving a multi-period optimization problem. The objective function presented in (2) consists in minimizing the electricity costs, considering the remuneration associated with PV based self-consumption for the day-ahead operation taking into account the expected PV generation and the domestic inflexible load.

$$\begin{aligned} \min \quad & -\lambda_{PV} \times Y_t^+ + \lambda_{Et} \times Y_t^- \\ \text{s.t.:} \quad & Y_t^+ - Y_t^- = P_{PVt} - P_{ULt} - P_t^m - P_t^j \\ & Y_t^+ \leq u_t M \\ & Y_t^- \leq (1 - u_t) M \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where:

- P_i^j , power in period i of appliance j
- λ_{PV} , electricity costs
- λ_{Et} , remuneration costs for injecting PV into the grid
- P_t^m , capacity of thermal appliance m
- P_{uLt} , uncontrollable loads
- P_{PV} , PV generation

For PV optimization decision variables Y^+ and Y^- were included in order to represent the situation when the PV is higher and lower than the residential consumption,

respectively. The binary variable u_i and the large positive constant M is used to impose either/or constraints. The same constraints of Model 1 were used.

IV. OPERATION SCENARIOS AND SIMULATION RESULTS

This section presents a set of scenarios upon which the energy management algorithms are tested. These are realistic cases, very likely to be found in daily-life applications.

To create these example scenarios to test the algorithm, public data sets [15] were used to model shiftable appliances and simulate uncontrollable loads, and standard values for the parameters of thermal appliances were considered. The previous formulation was implemented in C++ language to allow a performed-driven implementation. To test the optimization formulation a specific problem was created, representing a typical house, where 5 appliances were considered: three shiftable appliances - washing machine (WM) dishwasher (DW) and Clothes Dryer (CD); and two thermal - Air Conditioner (AC) and electric water heater (EWH). Since the control sample time was established at 15 min this means that 96 variables were created for each of the appliances to account for the intertemporal optimization of the day-ahead optimal scheduling.

The normal operating conditions presented in Figure 1 depicts a daily operation of the appliances (their activation) in a so-called typical day.

Figure 1. Baseline profile of all appliances regarding dynamic tariffs.

A. Dynamic Tariffs

In this work is considered a particular type of dynamic pricing referred to as the day-ahead hourly pricing [16]. Specifically, the Spanish dynamic tariff (Voluntary Price for Small Consumers (VPSC)) is used for simulation purposes. This tariff has roughly 12 millions of customers [17] and it is calculated for each day (hourly) and the prices are published at 8:15pm of the previous day. For this particular case the hourly prices of the 2nd of October of 2017 were considered.

Figure 2 presents an optimized scenario using the mathematical model 1, for a house with five controllable appliances. As shown in the figure, the consumption is shifted to the hours when the energy prices are lower.

Figure 2. Optimized profile of all appliances regarding dynamic tariffs.

1) *Contracted Power*: Considering the limitation of the instantaneous power that can be drawn from the grid, this scenario adds a constraint that limits the maximum power consumption in each time step, which cannot be violated under any circumstances to keep this approach as close to reality as possible. The appliances and parameters considered in this scenario are the same as in the previous section with a contracted power limitation of 6.9kW.

Figure 3. Optimized profile of all appliances regarding dynamic tariffs and limited power.

2) *End User Preferences*: The constraints already presented are mainly dependent on appliances parameters, or power limitations. However, when considering residential end-users the constraints need to be mainly focused on their preferences as already explained in Section III-A2. A scenario with a dishwasher and a washing machine are represented in Figure 4. For this setup the end user wants the dishwasher to work two times and to be finished at 7am and 3pm, and the washing machine to be ready at 7am. Consequently, the optimization process allocates the loads before the deadlines and at the cheapest hour.

Figure 4. Optimized profile of shiftable appliances regarding deadline constraints.

Additional constraints regarding availability for controlling specific loads are implemented and represented in Figure 5. In this case the end user has defined the deadlines for both appliances at 9h45am and for the second dishwasher cycle the

time limit 9pm. However in this case it is not considered smart appliances or other kind of remote control, being necessary a manual activation by the user and the most suitable hours to connect the appliances. In this case the intervals [6:15, 10:00] and [18:00, 23:00] are considered.

Figure 5. Optimized profile of shiftable appliances regarding deadline constraints and user availability.

B. Self-Consumption

For the self-consumption scenario, a PV unit installed at INESC TEC laboratory was considered. Constant energy prices (0.15/kWh) and PV injection remuneration (0.06/kWh, close to the average wholesale electricity market price) were assumed. Figure 6 presents an optimized scenario using the model 2. The PV generation is also included in the chart to facilitate the analysis of the results. As shown in the figure, the consumption is shifted to the hours when the PV generation is higher.

Figure 6. Optimized profile of all appliances regarding PV.

V. OPTIMIZATION PLATFORM FOR HOME ENERGY MANAGEMENT

The implementation of an energy management system was achieved in the AnyPLACE H2020 project that specified the functional, technical and technological requirements of such a solution. The main outcome is a SW and HW platform capable of interconnecting with other devices and systems. It is capable of storing the configuration and comfort preferences of users and with it produce optimal schedules of appliances (legacy and smart) for the following day. It is a highly customizable platform that incorporate functionalities from other existing systems as well as innovative ones related with the energy management purpose.

The SW modules were designed, implemented and embedded into a raspberry PI 3 computation core to produce a cost-effective solution that is flexible and adaptable to different

contexts. The platform is composed by different modules that incorporate the necessary functionalities for the home energy management, as depicted in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Functional Architecture

A. User Interface

The user interface (UI) module allows end-users the insertion of the configurations of appliances to be controlled, either manually or automatically, according the use and comfort preferences. A price discrimination can be inserted also, with up to 96 different periods (15 min each) of load consumption and generation to be defined. This allows the optimization algorithms to be ran and determine the best multi-temporal allocation of load and/or generation. Through this module, users can also select which type of optimization goal they intend to achieve. One particular aspect of the UI is its modularity that allows different functionalities to be added as new features that are to be supported by the platform. One example is the ability to consider additional restrictions formulation to allow a realistic implementation of the energy management system. The implementation of the UI is provided by either a local or a remote display. A web-version is available for both cases but an application is specifically available in the latter (Android and iOS devices).

B. Middleware

1) *Integrated Services Manager*: This module contains the functionalities used by the other modules, as well as those usually present in solutions also in the scope of domestic buildings (e.g. weather forecasting). This module manages alarms produced by other modules and making them available to the end-user via the UI. It is also responsible for the upgrade procedure of the entire middleware.

2) *Energy Manager*: The energy management methodology, detailed in section III, is part of the Energy Manager (EM) module. It collects data (local and external), analyzes preferences and configurations, to produce an optimal day-ahead schedule of loads and microgeneration, if existing. The

optimization problem formulation is made through the SCIP solver [18] that can be configured to produce an optimal or sub-optimal solution. The latter is only used if there is a time limitation for the EM to produce a suitable solution for the next-day operation. The energy manager integrates the restrictions that needed to be considered to make the platform usable in a wider variety of applications.

3) *Security Manager*: The security manager is responsible for the encryption and decryption of data exchange both locally and remotely. It includes the management of encryption keys and the detection of abnormal data exchange.

4) *Device Manager*: The automation implementation is provided by the device manager module that interact with devices and systems that are interconnected with the energy management platform. It is responsible for interconnecting with the OpenHAB automation platform from which it gathers information related to metering and monitoring and issues control set-points to associated devices and systems.

C. Operation Case

Using the UI an operation case was defined to validate the operation of the energy management platform. Comfort preferences and device configurations were defined the same way as the one presented in the previous section as depicted in Figure 5. Consequently, the platform embedded with the previously mentioned optimization algorithms, produced an optimal schedule for the following day, considering the same user availability and the price curve. As shown in Figure 8 the produced output is coherent with the one presented previously, thus showing the performance of the optimization procedures running in an actual platform the will be available to end-users in their households.

Figure 8. Energy Management Platform Optimal Schedule Output

The optimal schedule allocates the configured loads within the time intervals where the user is available to trigger them and in the time where the prices are lowest.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This paper proposes a cost effective energy management platform that allows end-users to implement energy efficiency actions through optimization algorithms and automation platforms.

Simulations were presented using real energy consumption and usage profile traces collected at homes and studying the system behavior of the algorithms. The presented results showed that this kind of solutions can have the necessary intelligence to characterize the energy use of an entire house and produce optimized schedules for variable components (e.g., energy consumption) and fixed components (e.g., contracted power / power cap).

An optimization platform for home energy management developed under the framework of the AnyPLACE H2020 project was presented. The platform composition and different functionalities for the home energy management were presented as the potential of the graphical user interface designed to collect comfort and energy usage preferences and to display the envisage day ahead scheduling to the end-users. The optimization algorithms were embedded in this platform and the produced results are similar to the ones achieve in the simulations. This platform will be available in a pilot in Germany where all these functionalities will be tested in a real environment and the achieved results analysis as well as further improvements will be part of future.

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